

Organizing for Open Science and Culture Change in Higher Education: An Institutional Logics Perspective

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Abstract

This study examines how a broad-based research university advances Open Science through a university-wide culture change programme. We draw on qualitative interviews and document analysis to provide an account of how efforts to institutionalize Open Science unfold across the regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive pillars of institutions. Using an institutional logics lens, we examine how these interventions are justified.

The case shows that interventions for change have attempted to balance managerial formalisation with academic autonomy and evolving notions of community. Limited formalisation provides flexibility but may generate ambiguity that, over time, calls for clearer shared goals. While regulative interventions can support normative changes and create momentum, deeper cultural-cognitive change remains gradual and susceptible to broader systemic pressures, including multi-level competition and contested understandings of 'quality'. Finally, we suggest that sustained progress in OS depends on participatory governance, visible leadership support, and continuous dialogue to identify consensus areas.

Keywords: Open Science, higher education, organisational change, institutional logics

1 Introduction

Changes in higher education institutions (HEIs) rarely unfold as straightforward, internally-driven processes. Today, universities are increasingly required to engage and communicate with a diverse range of stakeholders (Jongbloed et al., 2008), and thus change never happens in isolation, but instead is often triggered by the need to respond to broader societal forces (Olsen, 2007). Even as institutional leaders are tasked with setting strategic agendas and steering organisational priorities, universities have often been described as 'bottom-heavy', with a substantial part of authority exercised within the departments, disciplines, and professional communities rather than at the managerial apex (Clark, 1983;

Elken & Røsdal, 2017). In addition, the expansion in the range of missions, coupled with rising stakeholders' expectations, requires HEIs to make continuous efforts to balance their 'mission overload' (Enders & De Boer, 2009). In such an environment, university leaders face the challenge of reconciling external pressures with internal demands, while also aspiring to safeguard a distinctive organisational culture, even as competing visions exist in relation with, among other aspects, quality, social needs, and success criteria (Enders & De Boer, 2009; Olsen, 2007).

Traditionally, universities have been described as loosely coupled organisations, where subunits are weakly connected and operate with significant autonomy and decision-making is decentralized (Clark, 1983; Weick, 1976). This is partly due to the boundaries between disciplines that may result in academics aligning with different communities, sharing little beyond a common employer, with the department as the main cultural or subcultural unit with which academics most strongly identify (Silver, 2003). Another boundary exists between academics and administrators. Some authors have argued that these two groups have very distinct values and cultures and, in this case, administrators would appear to feel more identified with the organisation (Collinson, 2006). At the same time, in a context where higher education (HE) reforms have been inspired by New Public Management (NPM) ideas, universities have been described as 'organisational actors' (Krucken & Meier, 2006), which implies a reorientation from traditional collegial governance to corporate-like models, greater responsiveness to external forces, and strategic behaviour. Yet, this growing actorhood coexists with internal heterogeneity, as strategies initiated by central leadership are often resisted and reinterpreted by departments, resulting in different ways of implementing the same policies (Olsen, 2007). In our case, Open Science (OS), as a movement that has been incorporated in global policy agendas and to which HEIs have started to respond, illustrates this dynamic.

In the last few years, OS has been described as a movement and received attention in global and national policy agendas. Open access publishing and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data (Wilkinson et al., 2016) have become an integral part of requirements of some research funding agencies. We have seen the emergence of global (e.g. EU OS agenda, the UNESCO recommendation, and cOalition S) and country-level initiatives (e.g. the Dutch national OS plan, NPOS) aiming to foster OS approaches. These forces have pushed universities to respond by adopting institutional policies that align with external requirements. Yet, the context-specific character of

knowledge and the different interests underpinning OS, combined with the internal heterogeneity of HEIs, make it difficult to adopt a unified organisational approach.

In this study, we explore how Leiden University (LU) seeks to institutionalize OS as part of its university-wide Academia in Motion (AiM) programme. There are multiple definitions of OS, but this work is foregrounded in the broad definition provided in the “UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science” (UNESCO, 2021, p. 7):

an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.

We analyse how the stakeholders involved in the development of OS at LU manifest different institutional logics and examine the types of interventions that they consider important to promote OS at LU. Under the premises that: (1) change towards OS in HE is largely a response to external forces, but internal dynamics shape such change; (2) the understanding of OS differs across contexts and there are no standardized approaches; and (3) the rationales underpinning the transition to OS play a decisive role in shaping the trajectories that it might take; the questions that we try to answer in this work are as follow:

- (1) *What institutional logics are invoked in relation to OS and how compatible are they?*
- (2) *What change interventions are perceived as more suitable to move towards OS?*

2 Theoretical framework

In order to understand how Open Science unfolds from an organisational perspective, this study draws on two strands of institutional theory: the pillars of institutions and institutional logics. It is worth noting how the terms ‘institution’ and ‘organisation’ are used in this work, as universities are often referred to as higher education *institutions*, but analytically we treat our case as an organisation. When we refer to universities as institutions, what we mean is that they are highly institutionalised organisations. From this perspective, organisations, including universities, are instrumental actors, but their structures and practices are strongly shaped by their institutional field (Scott, 2013).

The pillars of institutions. Scott (2013) suggests three analytical elements to explain institutions. Based on the idea that “regulative systems, normative systems, cultural-cognitive systems—each of these elements has been identified by one or another social theorist as the vital ingredient of institutions” (p.59), the author devises three pillars:

regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive. These three can be placed in a continuum which goes from the conscious to the unconscious and, while separate, they are interdependent. Table 1 provides an overview of the content and rationale of each pillar, and each of them is further explained and contextualized in the findings section of this paper.

Table 1

Three pillars of institutions (Scott, 2013, p. 60)

	Regulative	Normative	Cultural-Cognitive
Basis of compliance	Expedience	Social obligation	Taken-for-grantedness Shared understanding
Basis of order	Regulative rules	Binding expectations	Constitutive schema
Mechanisms	Coercive	Normative	Mimetic
Logic	Instrumentality	Appropriateness	Orthodoxy
Indicators	Rules Laws Sanctions	Certification Accreditation	Common beliefs Shared logics of action Isomorphism
Affect	Fear Guilt / Innocence	Shame / Honor	Certainty / Confusion
Basis of legitimacy	Legally sanctioned	Morally governed	Comprehensible Recognisable Culturally supported

Institutional logics. In their seminal paper, Friedland & Alford (1991) introduced the concept of institutional logics in an attempt to bring back the role of agency to institutionalism and move away from the neo-institutional view that organisations can be explained through reproduction and stability. The authors described institutional logics as the broader belief systems and organising principles that structure how individuals and organisations understand and behave within institutions. Thornton & Ocasio (1999, p. 804) described institutional logics as “the socially constructed, historical pattern of material practices, assumptions, values, beliefs, and rules by which individuals produce and reproduce their material subsistence, organize time and space, and provide meaning to their social reality”. Building on Friedland & Alford's (1991) institutions of society, Thornton and colleagues (2012) introduced an interinstitutional system with seven major institutional orders: family, religion, corporation, profession, state, market, and community. While these institutional orders represent ideal types at the societal level, distinct field-level logics arise within specific contexts, either through the localisation of societal logics or through context-specific

developments. As discussed by Cai and Mountford (2022), this allows us to move from grand theory to middle-local level theory, integrating deductive and inductive reasoning aspects.

In this study, we combine these two approaches as, together, they offer an analytical lens to trace a change programme empirically. We treat the pillars not as causal mechanisms, but as analytical arenas in which field-level logics become locally instantiated and observable. This approach enables an exploration of how different logics are mobilized through regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive mechanisms to steer change. Figure 1 illustrates this relationship. The outer green circle represents the institutional logics that are salient in our specific context. The light blue arrows indicate that the logics manifest across the pillars, which are represented in the yellow circle. The orange arrows aim to show the dynamic process whereby all pillars are potential arenas where logics can manifest. The innermost circle represents change, understood as an ongoing process of reconfiguration within and across the regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive pillars. At any given time, certain logics may be more dominant and therefore more likely to shape interventions within particular pillars. However, this dominance is historically contingent and subject to reconfiguration.

Figure 1.

Dynamics of change interventions

3 Methods

3.1 Research context

The setting of this study was Leiden University, one of the fourteen public research universities in the Netherlands. Founded in 1575, it is the oldest university of the country. With over 33 000 students and more than 6 000 staff members (excluding the medical centre), its campuses spread across the cities of Leiden and The Hague, and comprise six faculties, a medical centre, and three interfaculty centres. Because of its broad-based character, LU is described as a highly decentralized university (Leiden University, 2015, p. 29):

Leiden University has traditionally been structured in such a way that management takes place at the lowest levels in the organisation, usually in one of the 27 institutes (...) The intention is to create maximum freedom for the academics themselves to determine the direction of their teaching and research. A strongly decentralised organisation is the appropriate structure for a broad-based research university.

LU introduced the programme Academia in Motion (AiM) in 2021. AiM seeks a culture change towards “an open knowledge community, with a focus on collaboration across boundaries, between colleagues, and between the university and society” (AiM steering group, 2023). The programme aspires to facilitate a shift in the academic environment, focusing on the diversification of academic careers, transparency, and leadership (Leiden University, 2021). It brings together OS and recognition and rewards (R&R) as two closely linked developments. R&R refers to the ongoing reform of research assessment and careers in the Netherlands. It is grounded in the position paper *Room for everyone’s talent: Towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics*, which advocates for a modernization of the current evaluation system (UNL et al., 2019).

What is Academia in Motion? (Dossier AiM, Leiden University)

Academia in Motion supports the culture change towards Leiden University as an open knowledge community, closely connected to society, that recognises and rewards everyone's contribution to our strategic goals.

In this open knowledge community:

- Scientific processes are more transparent, robust and inclusive.
- Knowledge flows more easily between universities and society.
- We acknowledge each other for the contributions we make to our shared strategic goals.
- Collaboration, innovation and knowledge sharing happens across disciplines and domains, and in diverse teams.
- There is room for curiosity and for a diversity of perspectives.

If we want a thriving, open knowledge community, we must innovate and act together.

3.2 Data collection

Data were collected through a combination of semi-structured interviews and policy insights from a document analysis, presented in a separate report (Parrón Cabañero, 2026).

A qualitative interview design was used to explore the evolution of OS at LU from the pre-development stages of AiM in 2018-19 until today. Figure 2 shows the milestones of AiM until the start of the programme's implementation.

Figure 2.

Timeline of AiM programme

The interview guide is available in this [link](#). Purposive and snowball sampling were used to recruit participants ($n = 12$). The inclusion criterion was involvement in the design of

OS policies at LU, and the group reflects a range of roles: researchers who participated in the process, policy advisors, and research support staff. Participants ranged from those who have been involved throughout the entire period to those who joined at a later stage, and from those still actively engaged to those who have since moved on (whether to other roles within LU or to positions elsewhere). Though their roles and involvement over time varies, all 12 interviewees have an insider's perspective on how OS came to become an important topic at LU and, together, they cover the whole timeframe. The reflections of this specific group of participants helped us capture how internal and external influences have shaped how OS is approached at LU and to better understand the policy design process. Interviews lasted between 40 and 130 minutes, with an average of about 60 minutes per interview, and were audio recorded. They were subsequently transcribed using the speech-to-text software Amberscript (Amberscript Global B.V., 2025), followed by a manual revision of the transcription to ensure accuracy.

3.3 Data analysis

The analysis was conducted by iterating between data and theory, moving back and forth between data reduction and representation, drawing conclusions and going back to the data to verify robustness. In an initial phase, we coded the interview transcriptions according to emerging themes, staying close to the data. While concepts from the theories underlying this study were kept in mind in this phase, the idea was to find patterns and allow diverse codes to emerge, using an inductive open coding approach. In a second round of coding, we started to explicitly connect the ideas identified in the first round with theoretical concepts, which allowed us to map the most prominent categories and the themes that are presented in the findings. The software for qualitative data analysis ATLAS.ti (*ATLAS.Ti Scientific Software Development GmbH, 2023*) was used for organising the data according to codes, memoing, and creating visualisations. This process facilitated a more systematic identification of themes and eased the process of writing up the findings. The codebook is available [here](#). To illustrate the findings, selected interview quotes are presented verbatim. As these reflect spoken language, occasional inconsistencies in grammar or structure are expected.

3.4 Reflexivity of the researcher

As an employee of LU myself and the main researcher in this project, I have reflected on my dual role and how this may influence the research process. Given that the unit under investigation is not my department, which creates a certain distance between my daily work and the case under research, I would not consider this study to fall under the category of

insider research—“complete members of organizational systems and communities in and on their own organizations” (Brannick & Coghlan, 2007), but neither would I say that I am an outsider. This section on reflexivity in itself is written in an attempt to enhance the analysis of the data and to make my interpretation more transparent.

On one hand, I believe that my position in the organisation provided me with familiarity, a level of access that outsiders may have found more limited, and an advantage to approach interview participants in most cases. On the other, familiarity may lead to being less attuned to nuances that are rendered invisible through taken-for-granted elements in the field. In addition, this position may involve navigating power asymmetries between researcher and participants, with ethical and methodological implications. To mitigate these concerns, the drafting of the ethics review form was used as a moment where the research team discussed and tried to anticipate potential tensions that might emerge during fieldwork. Furthermore, an agreement on the freedom of research within this project was drafted (access it [here](#)) to guarantee that findings from this project could be shared regardless of the potential negative consequences for the organisation. In short, while my position may have entailed challenges, it has allowed for valuable insights and meaningful discussions on the nature of the project. The additional measures mentioned above have been taken to further ensure the rigour of the study and its findings.

4 Findings

4.1 Visions for change: Perspectives on interventions across pillars

In this section, we present how interview participants frame change towards OS along the different pillars of institutions (Scott, 2013). The pillars are described as a continuum from conscious to unconscious: regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive. The findings are presented in that order, each time introducing the pillar and then relating the findings to it, and we connect the ideas to the institutional logics that inform them. However, as Scott cautions, the three pillars are analytical distinctions. In this regard, what we attribute to each pillar is rarely shaped by that pillar alone, but rather by the interaction of all three. Figure 3 presents the key findings across the pillars. In the figure, they are structured according to the central interventions, the challenges associated with each, and activities that could work as enablers to drive change, based on the interviews.

Figure 3.

Key findings

4.1.1 Regulative pillar.

The regulative pillar comprises aspects regarding regulations, monitoring, and sanctioning or incentivising. The main mechanism used is coercion, but this does not mean that there is repression or constraint, as activities under this pillar can also work by enabling action. In this regard, the reform of research assessment and changing incentives can fall under this pillar, especially if the recognition of OS practices is formalized for processes like hiring and promotions.

In the interviews, regulation is perceived as helpful to promote OS if used as a soft mechanism rather than imposed in a top-down manner. The institutional logic that underlies this pillar more prominently is the managerial logic, which is not unexpected as interventions in this area are normally initiated at the managerial level. The academic and community logics inform the process of policy design to ensure that policies support practices rather than exert control. By having policies that support OS practices, scholars can be confident that their organisation stands behind their actions, as P1 illustrates: “we need strong leadership to speak up and just stand for something that, that is spreading into the

awareness of people, but they also hear it from a guideline or from something else”. While participants value local approaches to OS, they express frustration at the lack of clear institutional guidelines to enable effective implementation, as P7 notes: “there's no clear institutional policy on infrastructure (...) so you have to sort it out yourself”.

A combination of top-down and bottom-up models seems to be the preferred approach to OS policymaking, yet realising this has proved challenging. The main strategy of the central AiM programme has been delegating the implementation to the faculties, under the rationale of allowing for localized approaches, aligning with the academic logic. Yet, faculties are hierarchically structured, and when a ‘faculty’ is mentioned, it often functions as a metonym for ‘dean’ in the interviews. This means that it is not necessarily easier to coordinate a bottom-up top-down approach at that level than it is at the university level. This has also created some challenges in the division of ownership, as P2 notes: “we want to have a group of people that actually can make decisions. But then, of course, we want the faculties on board, we need somebody that can represent the faculty. That's a problem we have not solved yet”. Attempts to implement a top-down bottom-up approach include the increased engagement of the AiM central team with faculty teams, known as FAiMs. Nonetheless, these teams are not yet considered to be mature across all faculties, as P8 indicates: “at the faculties, there are local teams, at least on paper: not all faculties are equally engaged”. Furthermore, the team composition is not as diverse as some participants had initially devised, as P10 notes:

An AiM team should be like all the different roles. So somebody for OS, somebody for social safety, somebody for HR policy, somebody for science communication (...) But now, because it's mostly just career policy, most of the teams are just a senior head of HR, some scientific staff, and if you're very lucky, also somebody who knows what open science is.

The state logic—which here includes supra-national aspects—is also visible in this pillar, as external initiatives have had a key role in the design and evolution of OS policies at LU. One of these was the OS roadmap of the League of European Research Universities (LERU), of which LU is a consortium member, mentioned in several occasions, for example: “The LERU agenda was very important because it is more or less obligatory for the university to respond to it” (P3) and “one of the external drivers, indeed, to create this group, was the LERU activities” (P6). In addition, the idea of having an OS programme is in itself seen as a pragmatic decision made by the university board largely as a result of developments outside the university, such as the position paper “Room for everyone’s talent”, by which Dutch universities were invited to develop a vision for R&R. Alongside with this, P5 notes the influence of national trends within FAiMs: “it [career policies] is such a hot

topic at the national level, and therefore also in each faculty, that some AiM teams are only working on that”.

Finally, it is worth noting that one participant highlighted a distinctive rationale for pursuing a formal, top-down, institution-wide programme: that the OS agenda cannot be disregarded by governing bodies such as boards and deans. This angle shows that formalisation is understood as a mechanism to ensure that bottom-up initiatives can get support, with the caveat that this may constrain the flexibility and diversity of practices emerging from the grassroots.

4.1.2 Normative pillar.

Within this pillar, Scott (2013) suggests to ask ourselves: “Given this situation, and my role within it, what is the appropriate behavior for me to carry out?” (p.65). The answer to this question is guided by values and what is thought to be considered appropriate. Considering the introduction of LU’s core values (innovative, connecting, responsible, and free) and the fact that AiM adheres to the value-based UNESCO recommendation, changes in the normative pillar are viewed as key in the programme.

In the interviews, the community, academic and managerial logics appear intertwined in this pillar. The presence of community is central as connection and collaboration between individuals and teams are presented as essential for enabling OS at LU. Yet, it appears closely linked with the academic logic, reflected in commitments with disciplinary standards and contextualised practices. In parallel, managerial coordination is also seen as an important condition to create awareness and guide behavioural change.

Within AiM, awareness efforts have taken place through dialogue between the central team and the faculties, generally engaging with people in administrative and management roles. These conversations have been fruitful: at the beginning, most of the effort of the AiM team went into explaining central concepts, while now, as P12 notes: “we have lots of conversations about these topics. There's very few people say, what are you talking about when we say these things”. The role of leadership is important, emphasising the need for visible and explicit support, as P1 indicates:

AiM has given us a vision and we're implementing this, but where is the backup, like my strong leadership saying? And now also we think this is so important that we just really stand behind it, I guess because AiM could just come across as yet another project by who exactly.

In addition, P11 notes: “what helps is that it's mentioned many more times. So the board of directors should mention it everywhere. State it in their documents”. Leaders often have

access to broad audiences, and these opportunities are considered key for disseminating the programme's ideas and signalling their commitment.

Beyond these communication channels, which do not actively engage with people on the ground, participants believe peer-to-peer dialogue is crucial. This includes creating opportunities for people who rarely interact to come together and exchange experiences, as P10 notes:

People would see it [OS] as extra work, whereas my intention was always like, no, this should replace some of the meetings you already have in the hopes that, by adding more people to existing meetings, you would get more of an exchange of ideas.

Awareness-raising is another topic that appears in the narrative. For instance, empowering OS champions, ideally within the faculties, as P4 notes: “if you want to bring change, you need to make sure that you do have champions within the faculties”. This is important for individuals to recognize the benefits and understand the practical implementation of OS. In addition, this addresses partly one of the most often mentioned challenges, which is what participants perceive as a lack of understanding of OS. The AiM programme seeks to integrate R&R and OS, a direction broadly endorsed in the interviews, as P7 suggests: “we would have more diverse and flexible academic career tracks, whereby the R&R procedure is led by the principles of open scholarship”. Participants stress the importance of recognising OS practices while creating space for diverse talents to be cultivated, enabling more varied career trajectories.

Awareness-raising also applies to cross-faculty connections, not only to learn from each other, but also to identify areas where consensus could be built, as P11 notes:

There are meetings with the faculties to share best practices, and I think that could be even more stronger because then you can show, okay, we take these practical steps and you might take them maybe as well or a little bit different, but there should be a common ground in these themes.

Finally, examples of good practice can give peers a more concrete sense of what OS could look like in practice, while also serving to persuade those in managerial positions. As P4 explains: “You need wonderful examples, striking examples that people think, well, that's really interesting. I never thought of that”.

4.1.3 Cultural-cognitive pillar.

In the cultural-cognitive pillar, we focused on descriptions that indicate taken-for-grantedness and orthodoxy of practices. This can be seen as the deepest layer of the institution, less visible than the other two pillars, and thus requires a more interpretative

exercise. In addition, the boundary between normative and cultural-cognitive arenas can be blurry. Under this pillar, we see culture as infrastructure in the sense that it provides the background conditions that are necessary for action, enabling or hindering practices.

In the interviews, when discussing changes that may fall under this pillar, we notice that challenges that may hinder OS emerge. The community logic is visible in the ambition to foster a culture that shifts from individual reputation and competition towards openness and cooperation as guiding principles. The academic logic is reflected in the idea that enabling OS requires a reconfiguration of professional practices and how academics organise their work, which also links back to the community logic. These two are also intertwined with managerial logics, since we see attempts to promote OS in a way that supports the organisation's strategy and advances LU's goals.

Overall, LU is portrayed as a traditional organisation, more reactive than proactive, and often slower than its Dutch peers. Together with the emphasis on its decentralized character, these traits can be seen to act as frameworks that shape the perception of what is feasible. Participants note that LU reacted to external developments rather than the specific needs of the organisation. P3 emphasizes this referring to LERU and European policies: "If that had not existed, I don't think anything would have happened. I mean, there were other things that I have opinions about, but if there is no external pressure, they can ignore it".

The interviews suggest that discipline-specific considerations and their implications for operationalising OS are at the centre. These concerns provide a rationale to have moved from a pillar-based to a value-driven approach to OS. In the interviews, either faculties or institutes are used as a proxy for discipline, and it is largely noted that implementation should be anchored at this level, for example by P8: "in the faculties you should choose your own focus (...) it should fit with your own context, your own strategic priorities and all of that". In parallel, the interviews, in line with the AiM documents, show an effort to strengthen organisational actorhood by promoting unified values, as P12 notes: "I think if you talk about OS, about R&R, it's about who are we as a university? What are our values? What do we value?". This participant emphasizes the depth of the transformation that AiM envisions, as it entails implications for academic norms and professional identity: "this is such a big change. It's about why we do things, what we reward. It's about the core of our academic work". Participants underscore that such a deep culture change "takes time", it is expected to be slow. However, a potential area for improvement that could facilitate progress is transparency in the policymaking process, perceived as slow and partial. For example, P11

notes: “I don't know why, but many documents are confidential (...) well, if it's confidential, I can just not do my work”.

In this pillar, beyond institutional characteristics, the dynamics under which academia operates more broadly are an essential part of the conversation. One participant argues that, in light of current attacks on truth and science, a reaction from universities has been to protect their professional legitimacy by closing down, that is, scholars might tend to adopt a defensive stance. This type of reaction hinders the principle of engaging with society in the scientific process. The multilayered competition across universities, departments, and individual scholars is part of the narrative as well. P4 explains that, initially, the themes addressed by AiM were not seen as something that would be “to the taste” of LU, a university that is “really eager to become the best”. ‘The best’ here is described in terms of awards, grants, excellence, and rankings and league tables position. This view has shifted, at least partly, seeing that AiM now advocates for broader and essentially more diverse and responsible approaches to research quality. However, one participant notes, more widely, perceptions of quality and evaluation are still based on metrics linked with publications. This participant states that some researchers appear to see OS as somewhat risky for their career advancement, especially when it comes to mobility across organisations and countries.

4.2 *Interplay and emergence of institutional logics*

Attending to the type of logic multiplicity by Besharov & Smith (2014), we observe what could be described as a contested programme. Three logics (academic, community, and managerial) are invoked as core to the design of the programme (high degree of centrality), and at the same time, these logics can be argued to potentially provide contradictory prescriptions for action (low degree of compatibility). Below, we explore how these logics are sometimes intertwined in the narratives and examine the emergence of the community logic.

Interplay of multiple logics.

Both the managerial logic and the academic logic are central in the development of the programme, as reflected in interview accounts as well as in OS policies at LU. This is in line with a well-documented phenomenon in HE that shows that universities have emerged as hybrid organisations (Jongbloed, 2015), where multiple logics coexist and can become intertwined (Reymert, 2024) or blended (Upton & Warshaw, 2017).

The narrative illustrates that these two logics often coexist and guide policy decisions. One participant, reflecting on their dual perspective as researcher and administrator, highlights the challenge of advancing initiatives while ensuring that all actors are consulted, which shows the tension between the managerial focus on efficiency and the academic emphasis on collegial consensus. Another participant notes that, while they believe that sharing practices across faculties could be very productive to advancing the OS programme, they perceive a fear that uniformity would enable the management to compare units and, as a result, increase pressure on them. This illustrates that standardisation is seen as a more effective mechanism from a managerial perspective, but there is a perceived risk of losing autonomy, and potentially resources, within academic units. The following quote of P8 illustrates the coexistence of academic and managerial logics, and the attempt to find a balance:

If you go for the one-size-fits-all solution, it's just clear for everyone. But it's supposed to happen and not everyone might be happy with it. But there is clarity. There is clarity, and you can move on much more efficiently.

Overall, participants agree with a degree of formalisation of Open Science practices (e.g., open access, data management, infrastructure), consistent with a managerial logic. However, they resist overly rigid policy frameworks, emphasising the importance of flexibility and disciplinary autonomy, thereby invoking an academic logic. Furthermore, they advocate participatory policy design processes, aligning with a community logic. As P7 notes, echoing a message present across interviews, “policy is mostly put upon top down, while practices are something that is many things that happen on the work floor. And what can you do, as a university management, to learn from what's going on in the work floor?” This illustrates a subtle tension between top-down policy making and bottom-up practices, while inviting to reflect on whether spaces can be created to integrate the two and, perhaps, reconcile academic, community, and managerial logics.

Emergence of community logic.

Community is a central theme of the AiM programme. Across the interviews, the community logic is invoked as participants consider that connecting people, units, and experiences is one of the things that the OS programme should accomplish. Some participants note that their most important role is connecting the academic community within the university. Going beyond the academic community, the interviews also pay attention to ensuring representation of people with varied profiles in the development of the programme,

as P6: “Try to be inclusive, and inclusive also means like, okay, maybe people who are a little bit farther away from OS”.

In terms of the community boundaries, some participants adopt a broad interpretation which includes societal actors, aligning with UNESCO, whereas others seem to restrict it to the university community. In this respect, P9 notes: “They don't mean the outside world. Whereas if I use the term community building, I'm talking about really collaborative, multi-stakeholder collaborations, but also outside academia. And that's not what they mean. They mean internal”. Hence, for some participants, the understanding of ‘community’ within AiM may potentially limit who is considered part of it.

The Open Science Community Leiden (OSCL) was involved in the design of the OS programme, as P6 explains: “We began to draft the programme, and we said, okay, we need to have input from the faculties, but also from the communities. And then we also invited to the group the Open Science Community Leiden”. Other communities are invited to be part of the AiM steering group, including the Leiden teacher academy, the Yong Academy Leiden, and the PhD association of the LUMC. However, P8 recognizes that this might not be enough for real co-creation: “these people kind of are supposed to represent a community within the university. But these communities are huge and diverse (...). But it's an attempt that we make indeed to have some degree of representation”. This points at a willingness to infuse the AiM programme with a community orientation, while also revealing the lack of established structures and institutional processes to enable genuine co-creation of strategies in the university.

5 Discussion

This study has analysed change interventions. Instead of focusing on whether change occurs, we have attempted to map where change efforts are directed. By focusing on interventions rather than assuming transformation, we can analyse uneven, layered, and sometimes contradictory change processes. Table 2 offers a simplified analytical abstraction of how different institutional logics are expressed across the three pillars, based on inferences from our data (from interviews and documents).

Table 2*Most salient institutional logics across institutional pillars in our case study*

Logic	Regulative	Normative	Cultural-cognitive
<i>Academic</i>	Policies support localized, discipline-specific practices; academics decide the rules	Moral duty to pursue integrity and quality; academic freedom as core value	Knowledge is structured in disciplines; quality comes from individual expertise; academics are recognized for their research activity
<i>Community</i>	Bottom-up practices receive policy support; rules come from community consensus	Moral duty to contribute to the well-being of the community; collective benefit as core value	Knowledge is legitimate when there is participation and inclusion of different stakeholders; quality improves through collaboration; all types of contributions to the community should be recognized
<i>Managerial</i>	Policies are seen as efficient tools to change behaviour; rules are set by the management	Moral duty to align contributions with the organisational goals; effectiveness as core value	Knowledge responds to external interests; quality can be measured through performance indicators; if you cannot measure it, it does not exist, and hence it cannot be recognized
<i>State</i>	Policies are aligned with national (and supra-national) frameworks; rules focus on compliance with funding bodies and alignment with external trends	Moral duty to respond to public demands; public accountability as core value	Knowledge serves society; quality is assessed according to public value; the university is recognized through its contribution to national (and supra-national) goals

Interventions in the regulative pillar are regarded as a tool for OS practices to become widespread as they create awareness. Policies may serve to modify behaviour, but the focus should be on targeted policies that support disciplinary needs. In AiM, implementation is decentralised to the faculties, with the central team acting in a supporting role. At that level, decisions on both what to focus on and how to put it into practice need to be made. However, this is not done through a clear mandate, and thus some faculties may engage more than others. The community and managerial logics in this pillar are reflected in the preferred top-down bottom-up approach to policymaking. Indeed, as Aarrevaara and

colleagues (2019) note, strategies are more meaningfully and easily integrated in daily practices when they are co-created with those who need to respond to it. However, the current organisational structures do not seem adequately equipped to accommodate this approach, which constrains the translation of this ambition into practice.

Within the normative pillar, values have become increasingly central in the discourse. In this regard, the AiM framework emphasizes that the 'ends' are more important than the 'means', providing room for situated decisions. The findings suggest that shifts within this pillar are seen as the most productive, while recognizing that such change interventions need to be driven by communities and through bottom-up practices. However, it is not clear in the findings whether participants have the same ideas in mind when they talk about 'bottom-up'. We also perceive a tension between, on one hand, reinforcing organisational actorhood by encouraging the community to align their goals with the organisational priorities (managerial logic), and on the other, promoting local enactments of AiM, where it may materialize in multiple forms shaped by academic and community logics. Such tensions between top-down priorities and bottom-up practices reflect the kind of institutional complexity that has been documented in the literature, where multiple logics coexist and interact within organisations (for example, Greenwood et al., 2011).

In relation to the cultural-cognitive pillar, the findings point to some enduring routines and cultural infrastructures that may hinder the implementation of OS policies and practices. One of them is the research system that strongly emphasizes an idea of excellence that encourages multilevel competition and relies on publication metrics as a proxy for quality. This is still visible explicitly in some faculties: for example, the Faculty of Science includes evaluations of staff with performance indicators regarding publications in journals with "an above average impact factor for the field". From the outset, AiM has been presented as a response to these system-wide issues, but the cultural-cognitive elements of institutions operate at multiple levels and other issues can be difficult to identify, especially when these are deeply embedded in the routines to the point that other behaviours would be inconceivable (Scott, 2013). In practice, this can result in tensions between the aspirational goals of OS and the enduring routines that continue to shape academic behaviour.

We suggest that, taking into account the processes unfolding over time, two institutional logics are dominant, academic and managerial, while a third one, community, is emerging. The state logic is also invoked, but its significance is limited: as noted by Pietilä and Pinheiro (2021), this is to be expected in the context of evolving NPM-inspired reforms HE. Some OS activities are formalized to some extent, like open access publishing and data

management, but different faculties and institutes are encouraged to implement OS according to their discipline-specific practices. In addition, the decentralized structure of LU means that supporting infrastructures are also fragmented, requiring adapted implementation. This approach allows for flexibility, but it is also perceived as vague. On one hand, by remaining intentionally ambiguous, a vision can accommodate different stakeholder priorities and minimize resistance; on the other, although early ambiguity can be productive, sustained change requires stabilisation through more concrete consensual goals that support organisational coordination (Gioia et al., 2012).

The findings indicate that the understanding of 'community' differs across participants and across initiatives. There are three main framings of community in the interviews. The first one sets boundaries around the university, in which OS may risk becoming a mechanism to reinforce the organisational position by increasing efficiency and providing a competitive advantage. Similar concerns have been noted, for instance, by Ross-Hellauer and colleagues (2022). The second framing emphasizes the academic community, and here OS can enhance the quality of academic work, professional integrity, and recognise scholarly contributions more broadly. While these are benefits for science, societal relevance is not fully considered. The third framing, more closely aligned with UNESCO, expands the notion of community to include stakeholders beyond the university and the academic community. This framing positions community as a collective of actors co-producing and using knowledge, rather than as a bounded academic or institutional group.

Lastly, drawing on the experiences of our participants in developing an OS programme, we identify several lessons for organisations pursuing similar initiatives. Regarding the regulative pillar, referring to external developments can help build a case for action. However, policies should avoid excessive rigidity and remain responsive to needs on the ground. Governance structures that integrate co-creation are therefore an essential condition not only to ensure relevance, but also to distribute responsibilities between central administration, faculties, and institutes in ways that ensure ownership.

Regarding the normative pillar, at an early stage, dialogue with middle-managers across faculties is crucial to build shared understanding and awareness. But more importantly, awareness among university staff must be created through peer exchanges, recognition of OS champions, sharing of good practices, and cross-faculty learning to identify areas of consensus. Visible support from leadership further signals legitimacy.

The cultural-cognitive pillar appears the most difficult both to influence and to interpret. As noted by Palthe (2014), changes in regulations may produce more rapid change

in some areas, while normative and cultural elements are more gradual, yet an alignment between all three is important for attaining organisational legitimacy (Carino et al., 2022; Trevino et al., 2008). In our case study, it seems that much of the misalignment between pillars is perceived to lie here. Even when regulative and normative efforts are in place, a fertile cultural ground for OS is not guaranteed. Several challenges extend beyond the institution itself and even beyond the field of HE, reflecting broader dynamics in society. For example, one participant mentioned attacks on science that could result in distancing research from society. Another is competition; in our case, competition at the individual level is emphasized, as career advancement still depends on established “rules of the game” and, in a global academic system where OS adoption varies widely, some fear career risks. At the same time, understandings of ‘quality’ need to shift from a narrow, metric-driven focus on research objects towards a more processual and broader conception that recognizes the plurality of academic responsibilities.

Finally, change should not be understood as a target state to be achieved, but as an ongoing process of adjustment. Alignment across pillars is never fully settled, it requires continuous reflection. As one participant aptly notes, “Academia in Motion is a very nice and elegant way of saying that you’re working on something that’s not finished yet, and you’re not sure about where it’s going to go to, where it’s going to lead us to”. This captures the open-ended character of a programme of this kind, where continuous learning and adaptation are necessary.

6 Conclusion

Leiden University’s AiM programme aims to steer a culture change towards an open knowledge community. Change is needed, according to the programme, because some issues have been raised in recent years: high workloads in universities, lack of transparency and accessibility of research results, and the way staff members are recognized (AiM steering group, 2023). The programme advocates for a faculty-based approach, where varied implementations of OS exist.

In its current form, the programme primarily engages with a culture change within the university and, to some extent the academic community. Nevertheless, if we assume that universities are socially embedded and policy-shaped institutions (Marginson, 2011), OS can serve as a site for renegotiating their public mission, reshaping how knowledge is produced, shared, and governed in HEIs. It offers an opportunity to move beyond internal reform and rearticulate the university’s mission in connection with society. What this may entail is

broadening the scope of the programme beyond research practices to explicitly include dimensions such as open education and other aspects included in the UNESCO recommendation which, at the moment, remain underdeveloped. In short, OS can be a mechanism for HEIs to contribute to a more equitable knowledge ecosystem, but they must move beyond the institutional reform agenda and align their missions more closely with their role in society and their public responsibility.

In terms of future research, as Besharov and Smith (2014) discuss, it is important to recognize that the compatibility and centrality of different logics might differ across subunits, which means that a single organisation can be characterized by multiple configurations of logic multiplicity. Future research could examine how institutional complexity is managed in practice across faculties. Organisations facing multiple logics may respond through different strategies, like decoupling, hybridization, or selective coupling, among others (see, for example, Greenwood et al., 2011 and Pache & Santos, 2013). Investigating how faculties enact the programme would provide insight into whether and how the programme is adopted, reconfigured, or contested at the operational level. Further attention is also needed to examine power asymmetries across subunits; that is, some agendas may shape which logics attain organisation-wide centrality, while other may remain comparatively peripheral.

7 References

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